

Have gardens protected mental health during the Covid-19 pandemic?

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Summary

This research aims to understand the relationship between access to greenspace and life satisfaction during the Covid-19 pandemic in the UK. Combining Ordnance Survey Greenspace Mastermap with the UK Longitudinal Household Study Covid sample, we use spatio-temporal analyses to track life satisfaction for the year from May 2020-2021 and examine whether access to public greenspaces and private gardens are protective against worsening mental health, particularly for those who have tested positive for Covid. Results of the preliminary analysis suggest a strongly positive association between access to private gardens and life satisfaction throughout the pandemic. We continue to explore how these associations relate to public greenspace access, and how these fluctuate across regions with varying deprivation. The results of the full analyses will provide evidence for interventions to support mental wellbeing during public health crises.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, gardens, greenspace, GWR, wellbeing

1. Introduction

Neighbourhood effects matter for a range of behaviours and outcomes, including mental illness (Mair et al., 2008), physical (in)activity (Sallis and Glanz, 2009), and chronic conditions (Vigo et al., 2016). Increasing urbanisation and socio-spatial inequalities have spotlighted poor urban health, reinforcing the necessity for built environments to support wellbeing (Macintyre et al., 2002). Wellbeing represents an individual's experience of their health, encompassing individual emotional, functional, and subjective aspects, as a vital, yet often overlooked, component of a flourishing society; good wellbeing benefits individual fulfilment and emotional resilience, as well as societal longevity, productivity, and prosperity (Fredrickson and Losada, 2005). One simple measure of mental wellbeing is life satisfaction (Fredrickson and Losada, 2005).

Improving urban greenspace may reduce wellbeing inequalities, by connecting residents to the natural environments within which humans evolved and are best adapted to flourish (Wilson, 1984), as well as providing opportunities to undertake wellbeing-promoting activities, such as socialising, relaxing, and physical activity (Hartig, 2014).

The Covid-19 Pandemic threw inequalities in access to greenspace into sharp relief, where 'stay at home' orders disproportionately impacted those without private greenspace and in areas of poorest greenspace provision, including BAME and less affluent communities (ONS, 2020). In addition, neighbourhood factors, including physical, social, and environmental deprivation account for a seven-year difference in life expectancy across England (Marmot et al., 2010) and disproportionate access to greenspace (ONS, 2020). Some communities are therefore more greatly impacted by their environments than others, due to contextual or compositional factors (Houlden, 2019). These factors raise the question of how wellbeing may have been impacted during the pandemic, for those in different environments with varying access to public and private greenspace.

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1.1. Research Questions

This research aims to understand the relationship between access to greenspace and life satisfaction during the Covid-19 pandemic in the UK, using geospatial analyses of longitudinal survey and map data, addressing the following Research Questions (RQs):

RQ1. How did life satisfaction change throughout the Covid-19 Pandemic?

RQ2. Does access to public and private greenspace vary across space, and by population characteristics?

RQ3. Have public and private greenspace been protective for mental wellbeing during the Covid-19 Pandemic?

2. Methods

2.1 Data

Individual data are drawn from the UK Household Longitudinal Panel Study (UKHLS), an ongoing biennial data collection since 2009. A bimonthly Covid sub-sample began in March 2020, which includes thorough socio-economic and demographic questions, alongside deprivation-experience variables (subjective financial situation, household-adjusted income), and individual life satisfaction, to capture mental wellbeing. Life satisfaction is measured through the question, ‘to what extent are you satisfied with your life nowadays?’, on a scale of 0 (‘not at all’) to 7 (‘completely’). Data from May 2020 to May 2021 are included for temporal analyses. The sample of residents in England with complete data is 17, 000 individuals. Individuals’ homes are located via their LSOA (Lower Super Output Area)

Designated public greenspaces are provided in shape files from OS MasterMap Greenspace layer. It contains polygons with the geographic location, size, and type of urban public greenspaces across the country (Ordnance Survey, 2010). Access to private greenspaces is included via a question within the UKHLS.

Figure 1 Distribution of Public Parks Across Leeds, as a proportion of LSOAs

2.2 Analysis

Preliminary analyses used LSOA shapefiles and Greenspace Mastermap to calculate the amount of greenspace in each individuals' local area. Temporal models are used to examine how life satisfaction varies throughout the pandemic and in different areas of England. Taking account of a range of individual factors allows us to examine how this varies according to socio-economic status and aspects of deprivation (RQ1)

Specifically, Linear and spatial regressions (Geographically Weighted Regression, GWR, Equations 1 & 2, **Figure 2**) are applied, to predict life satisfaction from access to both public and private greenspace, identifying which reveals the strongest association (RQ2).

$$LS_i = \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1i}GS_{1i} + \dots + \beta_{mi}x_{mi} + \varepsilon_{mi} \quad (1)$$

$$W_{ij} = e^{-0.5\left(\frac{d_{ij}}{b}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where LS_i is the life satisfaction outcome for individual i , β_m represent the regression coefficients for variables x_m , and ε_{mi} is the localised error term. The data points included in each individual-level model are weighted according to proximity; weights are distributed according to Gaussian kernel of bandwidth b , at distance d between individual i and each neighbour j , enabling to coefficients within the model to vary across space. Controls for a range of socio-economic, demographic, and local-area deprivation feature in all analyses. The spatial distribution of association facilitates inference of additional underlying contextual factors.

Figure 2 Demonstration of neighbour weighting calculations in Geographically Weighted Regression

This model then extends to Geographical and Temporal Weighted Regression (GTWR), which computes weights according to the relative spatial S and temporal T positions of the data, at each time t , across the 6 (alternating) months of data available between May 2020 and 2021 (Equation 3):

$$W_{ijST}^t = e^{-\left(\frac{d_{Sij}}{b_{St}}\right)^2} \times e^{-\left(\frac{d_{tij}}{b_T}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

To model associations between different wellbeing outcomes and the main types of useable urban greenspace, five categories are stratified: private gardens natural areas, formal parks, and outdoor sports facilities, and model moderation included by theorised mechanisms of social interaction, physical activity, and nature connection (RQ2). This facilitates consideration of temporal variation and the

relative importance of the various greenspace characteristics.

Finally, spatio-temporal differences in access and outcomes for potentially disadvantaged groups are examined, according to gender, life stage, ethnicity, and local-area deprivation, creating opportunity maps to identify social, cultural, and environmental sub-groups most vulnerable to the poorest provision (RQ3). We examine interactions between access to greenspaces, dates of lockdown restrictions, and whether individuals have tested positive for Covid-19, to explore whether greenspace may be protective against poorer wellbeing during the Pandemic.

3. Results

While full analyses are ongoing, preliminary results reveal how life satisfaction has fluctuated throughout the year May 2020- May 2021, rising slightly throughout the summer months, and then decreasing as more lockdown restrictions were brought in during the Autumn and Winter of 2020 (Figure 3).

Figure 2 Individual life satisfaction has fluctuated between May 2020 and May 2021.

Results of the linear regression model show a strong and significant positive association between having access to a private garden and life satisfaction during the first wave of the Covid-19 Pandemic, an association which again fluctuated but remained strongly positive throughout the year to May 2021. As would be expected, the number of people testing positive for Covid-19 increased drastically throughout the period of the data, with a weaker but negative association with life satisfaction. Interestingly, interactions between having private garden access and testing positive were not significant.

Table 1 Results of Linear Regression Model predicting Life Satisfaction

Variable	<i>B</i> Coefficient	<i>p</i>
Garden Access	1.178	<0.001
Has had Covid-19	-0.275	0.009

The spatial associations between greenspace access and life satisfaction are still ongoing, though initial results demonstrate that associations vary across space, implying that greenspace may be more protective in some areas than others.

The results of the full analyses will provide evidence base to inform future research and public health planning, while informing interventions to support mental health and wellbeing during public health crises.

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Biography

Dr Victoria Houlden is a Lecturer in Urban Data Science in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. Her research aims to understand the ways in which spaces and places embody inequalities, and the social structures influencing how people relate to their environment, particularly how urban landscapes impact wellbeing.